

ISic3212

I.Sicily inscription 3212

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---]δ' ἀπέδω[κ][][---]
2. [---]τρον Διοδω[ρ][][---]
3. [---] πολλὰ καμῶ[ν][---]
4. [---]ΚΥΠΑΛΛ[---]
5. [---]Ι[---]

Apparatus

Korhonen 2004

Translation (eng)

...Diodoros (Diodora?) after much toil...

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645532

PHI 316203

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 54.0922

Korhonen, K. 2004. Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione. Helsinki. At 47

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